

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES AND FIGURES FOR METABOLIC RESILIENCE IN
DAIRY GOATS: INSIGHTS FROM NUTRITIONAL CHALLENGE AND MILK
UNTARGETED METABOLOMICS

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Interpretive Summary :

Frequency of nutritional challenges is expected to increase with climate change, and dairy goats will need to manage these challenges to maintain health and productivity. We studied how goats with different longevity and resilience responded to an acute underfeeding period. Using milk metabolomics, we found that modifications of milk concentration in certain molecules in response to a nutritional challenge were linked to resilience and longevity genetic background. These results suggest that milk content in certain metabolites can reveal how well goats handle nutritional stress and may help identify resilient animals.

Table S1 : Summary of sire EBV for functional longevity and the number of daughters included in the study

	EBV for functional longevity	Number of offspring
Sire 1	-269	2
Sire 2	-216	1
Sire 3	-204	7
Sire 4	-194	3
Sire 5	-186	2
Sire 6	-133	5
Sire 7	-69	4
Sire 8	-1	2
Sire 9	34	6
Sire 10	68	1
Sire 11	98	2
Sire 12	99	4
Sire 13	145	1
Sire 14	203	6
Sire 15	242	3
Sire 16	242	4
Sire 17	273	9
Sire 18	311	5
Sire 19	365	1
Sire 20	NA	1
Sire 21	NA	1

Estimated breeding values (EBV) for functional longevity and the number of offspring per sire included in the study. The EBV indicates genetic potential for longevity excluding productivity-related culling. Two sires have no available EBV data (NA).

Table S2 : Least squares means (LSmeans) and changes during a 2-day underfeeding challenge for zootechnical milk production parameters, 13 milk metabolites, and 1 enzyme in 70 Alpine goats. A Type III ANOVA was used to compare resilience groups (LOW_RES and NORM_RES), adjusting for litter size (1 vs. 2+) and experimental cohorts (3 farm/year). Measurements were taken at the start (36 ± 5 days in milk) and at the end (38 ± 5 days in milk) of the challenge (2 days with access to straw only) during morning milkings. Comparisons between LOW_RES and NORM_RES groups are presented for pre-challenge (D0) concentrations and changes during the challenge (D2–D0).

	Pre-challenge (D0)			Challenge (D2-D0)		
	LSmeans of LOW RES (SE)	LSmeans of NORM RES (SE)	P-value	LSmeans of LOW RES (SE)	LSmeans of NORM RES (SE)	P-value
BHB (microM)	28.58 (1.48)	27.85 (0.89)	0.67	20.69 (5.17)	17.37 (3.13)	0.58
Chol (microM)	261.14 (13.06)	258.63 (7.9)	0.87	440.70 (32.76)	366.60 (19.82)	0.05
Choline (microM)	1.32 (0.07)	1.22 (0.04)	0.19	2.35 (0.16)	2.07 (0.10)	0.14
Gal (microM)Glu	63.08 (4.75)	66.76 (2.87)	0.50	29.23 (5.71)	31.06 (3.45)	0.78
(microM)	218.62 (19.73)	220.37 (11.93)	0.94	-66.67 (18.59)	-75.67 (11.24)	0.67
Glu6P (microM)	61.18 (2.26)	64.74 (1.37)	0.17	-34.26 (3.24)	-20.20 (1.96)	< 0.01
Glutamate (microM)	177.37 (16.67)	209.62 (10.08)	0.10	-115.74 (15.07)	-110.54 (9.12)	0.76
isocitrate (microM)	181.14 (13.86)	188.41 (8.38)	0.65	82.31 (13.57)	50.78 (8.21)	0.05
LDH (UI)	9.8 (0.9)	11.54 (0.55)	0.1	48.72 (4.32)	49.54 (2.61)	0.87
Malate (microM)	82.89 (8.11)	95.73 (4.91)	0.17	-57.74 (7.65)	-60.95 (4.63)	0.72
NH ₂ (glutamate micro eqv)	1567.52 (85.63)	1677.41 (51.79)	0.27	-439.33 (75.32)	-179.24 (45.56)	< 0.01
TAG (mM)	56.21 (3.17)	52.37 (1.92)	0.29	63.15 (5.09)	56.24 (3.08)	0.24
Urate (microM)	45.75 (6.33)	49.07 (3.83)	0.65	44.63 (9.54)	47.11 (5.77)	0.82
Urea (mM)	6.75 (0.28)	6.37 (0.17)	0.24	-1.90 (0.32)	-1.01 (0.20)	0.02
MY (kg/d)MFC	3.04 (0.12)	2.91 (0.07)	0.34	-1.81 (0.10)	-1.63 (0.06)	0.13
(g/kg)MFP (g/kg)	44.54 (1.21)	42.01 (0.73)	0.07	39.78 (1.95)	34.69 (1.18)	0.03
SCS	32.66 (0.52)	33.39 (0.32)	0.23	3.75 (0.73)	1.20 (0.44)	< 0.01

Glucose-6-phosphate (Glu6P), glucose (Glu), galactose (Gal), β -hydroxy-butyrate (BHB), NH₂ (free amino groups), triacylglycerols (TAG), cholesterol (Chol) and lactate dehydrogenase enzyme (LDH). Milk performance: daily milk yield (MY), ratio of fat content to protein content (F:P ratio), fat content (MFC), protein content (MPC), somatic cell score (SCS), calculated as $SCS = \log_2(SCC / 100\ 000) + 3$, where SCC is expressed as cells per mL.

Table S3 : Least squares means (LSmeans) and changes during a 2-day underfeeding challenge for zootechnical milk production parameters, 13 milk metabolites, and 1 enzyme in 138 Alpine goats. A Type III ANOVA was used to compare resilience groups (LOW_RES and NORM_RES), adjusting for litter size (1 vs. 2+) and experimental cohorts (3 farm/year). Measurements were taken at the start (36 ± 5 days in milk) and at the end (38 ± 5 days in milk) of the challenge (2 days with access to straw only) during morning milkings. Comparisons between LOW_RES and NORM_RES groups are presented for pre-challenge (D0) concentrations and challenge-induced changes (D2–D0).

	Pre-challenge (D0)			Challenge (D2-D0)		
	LSmeans of LOW RES (SE)	LSmeans of NORM RES (SE)	P-value	LSmeans of LOW RES (SE)	LSmeans of NORM RES (SE)	P-value
BHB (microM)	28.58 (1.02)	27.85 (0.62)	0.54	20.69 (3.59)	17.37 (2.17)	0.42
Chol (microM)	261.14 (9.06)	258.63 (5.48)	0.81	440.7 (22.73)	366.6 (13.75)	0.01
Choline (microM)	1.32 (0.05)	1.22 (0.03)	0.06	2.35 (0.11)	2.07 (0.07)	0.03
Gal (microM)	20.99 (2.61)	23.59 (1.58)	0.39	3.27 (1.85)	0.09 (1.12)	0.14
Glu (microM)	95.31 (9.05)	82.47 (5.47)	0.22	-40.24 (9.55)	-33.24 (5.78)	0.52
Glu6P (microM)	20.06 (1.2)	23.57 (0.72)	0.01	-10.69 (1.90)	-4.16 (1.15)	< 0.01
Glutamate (microM)	177.37 (11.56)	209.62 (6.99)	0.02	-115.74 (10.46)	-110.54 (6.33)	0.67
isocitrate (microM)	181.14 (9.61)	188.41 (5.82)	0.51	82.31 (9.42)	50.78 (5.7)	< 0.01
LDH (UI)	9.8 (0.63)	11.54 (0.38)	0.02	48.72 (2.99)	49.54 (1.81)	0.81
Malate (microM)	82.89 (5.63)	95.73 (3.40)	0.05	-57.74 (5.31)	-60.95 (3.21)	0.60
NH ₂ (glutamate micro eqv)	1567.52 (59.40)	1677.41 (35.93)	0.11	-439.33 (52.25)	-179.24 (31.6)	< 0.01
TAG (mM)	56.21 (2.20)	52.37 (1.33)	0.13	63.15 (3.53)	56.24 (2.14)	0.09
Urate (microM)	45.75 (4.39)	49.07 (2.66)	0.51	44.63 (6.62)	47.11 (4.00)	0.74
Urea (mM)	6.75 (0.19)	6.37 (0.12)	0.09	-1.9 (0.23)	-1.01 (0.14)	< 0.01

Glucose-6-phosphate (Glu6P), glucose (Glu), galactose (Gal), β -hydroxy-butyrate (BHB), NH₂ (free amino groups), triacylglycerols (TAG), cholesterol (Chol) and lactate dehydrogenase enzyme (LDH).

Table S4 : Correlation between sire EBV for functional longevity (n = 19) and offspring metabolite levels (n = 68) at pre-challenge and their changes during a nutritional challenge, weighted by number of offspring. Metabolite annotations were obtained via MS/MS analysis. Displayed correlations have raw p-values < 0.05; FDR corresponds to BH-corrected p-values.

Mass_RT_Formula	Annotation	Pre-challenge/challenge (Tendency*)	Corr w/EBV	stdErr	P_Value	FDR_P_Value
M123.0554T1.19	Nicotinamide	Change (Decrease)	-0.49	0.21	0.03	0.42
M146.1652T0.71	Spermidine	Pre-challenge	0.53	0.20	0.02	0.65
M146.1652T0.71	Spermidine	Change (Increase)	-0.50	0.21	0.03	0.41
M218.1389T3.16	Propionylcarnitine	Change (Decrease)	-0.40	0.22	0.09	0.53
M262.1286T1.19_1	C4-DC carnitine	Change (Decrease)	-0.76	0.16	< 0.00	0.01
M480.3088T15.44	PE(0:0/18:1(11Z))	Pre-challenge	0.43	0.22	0.06	0.65
M480.3088T15.44	PE(0:0/18:1(11Z))	Change (Increase)	-0.46	0.21	0.04	0.41

*"Tendency" indicates the mean trend during the challenge.

Figure S1 : Correlation between sire EBV for functional longevity (n = 19) and offspring metabolite levels (n = 68) at pre-challenge (D0) and their changes (logFC) during a nutritional challenge, weighted by the number of offspring. Metabolites are described by their mass and retention time obtained via LC-MS, and whether they correspond to baseline (D0) or change (logFC), as indicated by the labels M_XXT_XX_D0 or M_XXT_XX_LogFC. All displayed metabolites show significant or suggestive correlations after FDR correction (FDR < 0.10). The correlation coefficient (r) represents the weighted Spearman correlation computed using the weighted R package.

